

Views on Geopolitical Strategic Plans of Superpower Countries

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Abstract

This paper aims to contribute the facts that I studied about geopolitical strategic plans of superpower countries and how to approach the geopolitics of Myanmar and neighboring countries to develop governance. There are many strategic plans (Sea power, Land power, Rimland, Indo-Pacific, BRI, etc.) to understand geopolitics and geoeconomics. Superpower countries competed with each other to maintain their power and enhance their militaries and how to control the world's countries. You will also see the ending of Western World and the rise of the Eastern world from this paper. **Geopolitics** is a very important subject in world countries to maintain their powers for a long time. Geopolitical events, particularly conflicts, represent acute disruptions for the ports involved. As a result of conflicts, port infrastructure can be damaged, pillaged and unmaintained; this would undermine its capacity to support basic demand for essential goods. The word geopolitics was originally coined by the Swedish political scientist Rudolf Kjellén about the turn of the 20th century, and its use spread throughout Europe in the period between World Wars I and II (1918–39) and came into worldwide use during the latter. **Superpower** describes a state or supranational union that holds a dominant position characterized by the ability to exert influence or project power on a global scale. This is done through the combined means of economic, military, technological, political, and cultural strength as well as diplomatic and soft power influence. Traditionally, superpowers are preeminent among the great powers. While a great power state is capable of exerting its influence globally, superpowers are states so influential that no significant action can be taken by the global community without first considering the positions of the superpowers on the issue. This paper refers to the view of geopolitical strategic plans of superpower countries and how to approach regional geopolitics of Myanmar. This paper described the theories of geopolitics, geoeconomics and strategic plans of superpower countries.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world's most powerful countries are determined by a variety of factors, including economic strength, military might, and cultural influence. In terms of economic power, the United States remains the world's largest economy, with a GDP of over \$27.61 trillion in 2024. China is the world's second-largest economy, with a GDP of over \$16 trillion, but its economic growth has been slowing down in recent years. In terms of military power, the United States has the world's most powerful military, with a budget of over \$740 billion in 2021. Its military includes more than 1.3 million active-duty personnel, over 8,000 tanks, and over 11,000 aircraft. Russia and China are also considered to have powerful militaries, with modern weapons systems and advanced technology. The United Kingdom and France also have significant military capabilities and are among the few countries with nuclear weapons.

Cultural influence is another factor that contributes to a country's power. The United States has the most significant cultural influence in the world, with American music, movies, and television shows being popular around the world. Other countries, such as Japan and South Korea, have also become significant cultural influencers in recent years, particularly in the realm of popular music. Overall, the most powerful countries in the world are those with a combination of economic, military, and cultural power. The United States remains the most powerful country in the world, followed by China and Russia. However, the balance of power may shift in the coming years as countries like India and Brazil continue to grow economically and assert themselves on the global stage.

1.1 What is Superpower?

The term "global superpowers" first appeared after World War II and was applied to the United States and the Soviet Union. The U.S. and the U.S.S.R. dominated world affairs during the Cold War, and neither made a move without considering the reaction of the other (hence Britannica's reference to cooperation). Some experts argue that only the U.S. remained a superpower after the Soviet Union dissolved/downsized to become Russia in the early 1990s. Today, opinions differ as to whether the U.S. remains the only global superpower or whether it is one of a small, select group of superpowers. World superpowers, also called global superpowers, are the world's most powerful nations. Superpowers assume dominant positions on the world stage and are characterized by their ability to exert influence or project power (or aid) on a global scale. The economic, military, and foreign policies of superpowers are watched closely by other countries and can greatly impact the rest of the world.

1.2 What is Geopolitics?

Geopolitics is the study of how geography affects politics and international relations. Within the field of geopolitics, analysts study actors—the individuals, organizations, companies, and national governments that carry out political, economic, and financial activities—and how they interact with one another. In the broader context, geopolitics is regarded as the political type of geo-adaptation of society. From this perspective, it is suggested that the following idealized types of geopolitical models be identified, namely: natural-geographical, socio-geographical, activity-related, and chrono geopolitical. Geopolitical Economy examines the significance and nature of free trade agreements (FTAs), the primary policy tool through which modern nations seek access to international markets and promote economic growth.

1.3 Elements of the Strategies of Superpower

Geopolitical strategic plans of superpower countries can vary over time and depend on their specific goals and circumstances. Here are some common elements often seen in the strategies of superpower countries;

Maintaining Regional Influence: Superpower often seek to maintain or expand their influence in key regions. For example, the United States has historically focused on the Americas, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific.

Economic Interests: Protecting economic interests, including access to resources and markets, is a fundamental part of their strategy. This might involve trade agreements, economic partnerships, and infrastructure development.

Military Power: Superpowers typically maintain robust military capabilities to deter potential adversaries and protect their interests. This includes both conventional and nuclear forces.

Alliances and Partnerships: Superpowers form alliances and partnerships to strengthen their position. NATO, for example, is a key alliance for the United States.

Diplomacy and Soft power: Diplomacy and soft power tools, like cultural exchanges, education, and international aid, are used to shape global perceptions and gain influence. Cybersecurity and Information

Warfare: In the modern era, cyber capabilities and information warfare play a significant role in superpower strategies.

Global Governance: Superpowers often seek to shape international institutions and norms to align with their interests and values.

Containment or Competition: Superpowers may engage in containment strategies against rival powers or engage in competition for influence in regions of strategic importance.

Energy Security: Ensuring access to energy resources is a priority, and some superpowers seek to diversify their energy sources and routes.

These strategies can evolve over time and the specific priorities and actions of superpowers may have changed since my last update. It's essential to refer to more recent sources and analyses for the latest information on the geopolitical strategies of specific countries. Predicting which countries will become superpowers in the future is challenging and can depend on various factors, including economic growth, political stability, military capabilities and global influence.

1.4 Characteristics of Superpower Countries

Superpower countries often referred to as superpowers are nations that wield significant and influential power on the global stage. These countries have the capacity to shape international events, influence the behavior of other nations, and protect their military, economic, and diplomatic power worldwide. *Characteristics of superpower countries* typically include.

Economic Strength: Superpowers have large and robust economies, often with a substantial GDB, extensive international trade networks and significant influence over global financial systems.

Military Power: They maintain formidable military capabilities which can include nuclear arsenals, advanced conventional forces and the ability to project military force beyond their borders.

Political influence: Superpowers often hold key positions in international organizations and play a significant role in shaping global governance and international norms.

Diplomatic Reach: They have the ability to engage in diplomacy and negotiations on a wide range of international issues and conflicts. **Culture and Soft Power:** Superpowers can exert cultural influence through media, entertainment, education and language. They often use soft power tools to shape international perceptions and relationships.

Resource Access: They secure access to critical resources including energy, minerals and food to support their economies and maintain strategic advantages.

Historically the term superpower has been most commonly associated with countries like the United States and Soviet Union during the Cold War. In the modern era, China is often considered a rising superpower due to its economic and military growth. It is important to note that the concept of superpower status is fluid and can change over time and the term itself may evolve as global power dynamics shift. Additionally, some experts argue that the 21st century is characterized by a more multipolar world where power is distributed among multiple influential actors including non-state entities and international organizations. Studying the geopolitical views and strategies of world countries requires a multifaceted approach, analysis and staying informed about international affairs. Here is a step-by-step guide on how to study geopolitical views effectively.

2. GEOPOLITICAL STRATEGIC PLANS OF SUPERPOWER COUNTRIES

2.1 Range of Factors in Geopolitical Strategic Plans

The geopolitical strategic plans of countries can vary widely and are influenced by a range of factors including national interests, regional dynamics and global events.

United States: **Maintain Global Influence:** The U.S seeks to maintain its status as a global superpower and promote its values and interests around the world. **Alliance:** The U.S maintains alliances such as NATO and regional partnerships to bolster its security and influence. **Pivot to Asia:** A focus on the Asia-Pacific region to counterbalance China's rise. **Promote Democracy:** Historically the U.S has aimed to promote democratic governance and human rights globally.

China: **Economic Expansion:** China aims to continue its economic growth and expand its influence through initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). **Regional Dominance:** Asserting control over disputed territories in the South China Sea and enhancing its regional influence. **Global Trade:** Strengthening trade relationships to secure resources and markets.

Russia: **Regional Influence:** Reasserting influence in neighboring countries and former Soviet states. **Counter Western Influence:** Countering Western influence, particularly in Eastern Europe and the Middle East. **Energy Leverage:** Using energy resources as a geopolitical tool, especially in Europe.

India: Regional Power: Expanding influence in South Asia and the countering Chinese influence. Economic Growth: Promoting economic development and trade in the region. Global Role: Aspiring to a more significant role in global governance and international institutions.

European Union: Integration: Deepening political and economic integration among member states international diplomacy. Security: Addressing regional security challenges particularly in Eastern Europe and the Mediterranean. The world's most powerful countries also are the ones that consistently dominate news headlines, preoccupy policymakers and shape global economic patterns. Their foreign policies and military budgets are tracked religiously. When they make a pledge, at least some in the international community trust – or fear – they will keep it. These countries project their influence on the world stage.

2.2 Early Superpowers

No agreed definition of what a superpower exists and may differ between sources. However, a fundamental characteristic that is consistent with all definitions of a superpower is a nation or state that has mastered the seven dimensions of state power. The term was first used to describe nations with greater than great power status as early as 1944, but only gained its specific meaning with regard to the United States and the Soviet Union after World War II. This was because the United States and the Soviet Union had proved themselves to be capable of casting great influence in global politics and military dominance. The term in its current political meaning was coined by Dutch-American geostrategic Nicholas Spykman in a series of lectures in 1943 about the potential shape of a new post-war world order. This formed the foundation for the book *The Geography of the Peace*, which referred primarily to the unmatched maritime global supremacy of the British Empire and the United States as essential for peace and prosperity in the world.

A year later, in 1944, William T. R. Fox, an American foreign policy professor, elaborated on the concept in the book *The Superpowers: The United States, Britain and the Soviet Union — Their Responsibility for Peace* which spoke of the global reach of a super-empowered nation. Fox used the word superpower to identify a new category of power able to occupy the highest status in a world in which—as the war then raging demonstrated—states could challenge and fight each other on a global scale. According to him, at that moment, there were three states that were superpowers, namely the United States, the Soviet Union, and the United Kingdom, The British Empire was the most extensive empire in world history and considered the foremost great power, holding sway over 25% of the world's population and controlling about 25% of the Earth's total land area, while the United States and the Soviet Union grew in power before and during World War II. The UK would face serious political, financial, and colonial issues after World War II that left it unable to match Soviet or American power. Ultimately, Britain's empire would gradually dissolve over the course of the 20th century, sharply reducing its global power projection. The 1956 Suez Crisis suggested that Britain, financially weakened by two world wars, could not then pursue its foreign policy objectives on an equal footing with the new superpowers without

sacrificing convertibility of its reserve currency as a central goal of policy. As the majority of World War II had been fought far from its national boundaries, the United States had not suffered the industrial destruction nor massive civilian casualties that marked the wartime situation of the countries in European Asia. The war had reinforced the position of the United States as the world's largest long-term creditor nation and its principal supplier of goods; moreover, it had built up a strong industrial and technological infrastructure that had greatly advanced its military strength into a primary position on the global stage. Despite attempts to create multinational coalitions or legislative bodies (such as the United Nations), it became increasingly clear that the superpowers had very different visions about what the post-war world ought to look like and after the withdrawal of British aid to Greece in 1947, the United States took the lead in containing Soviet expansion in the Cold War. The two countries opposed each other ideologically, politically, militarily, and economically. The Soviet Union promoted the ideology of Marxism–Leninism, planned economy, and a one-party state whilst the United States promoted the ideologies of liberal democracy and the free market in a capitalist market economy. This was reflected in the Warsaw pact and NATO military alliances, respectively, as most of Europe became aligned with either the United States or the Soviet Union. These alliances implied that these two nations were part of an emerging bipolar world, in contrast with a previously multipolar world.

The idea that the Cold War period revolved around only two blocs, or even only two nations, has been challenged by some scholars in the post–Cold War era, who have noted that the bipolar world only exists if one ignores all of the various movements and conflicts that occurred without influence from either of the two superpowers. Additionally, much of the conflict between the superpowers was fought in proxy war, which more often than not involved issues more complex than the standard Cold War oppositions.

After the Soviet Union disintegrated in the early 1990s, the term hyperpower began to be applied to the United States as the sole remaining superpower of the Cold War era. This term, popularized by French foreign minister Hubert Védrine in the late 1990s, is controversial and the validity of classifying the United States in this way is disputed. One notable opponent to this theory is Samuel P. Huntington, who rejects this theory in favor of a multipolar balance of power. Other international relations theorists such as Henry Kissinger theorize that because the threat of the Soviet Union no longer exists to formerly American-dominated regions such as Western Europe and Japan, American influence is only declining since the end of the Cold War because such regions no longer need protection or have necessarily similar foreign policies as the United States. According to Lyman Miller, "the basic components of superpower stature may be measured along four axes of power: military, economic, political, and cultural (or what political scientist Joseph Nye has termed "soft power"). In the opinion of Kim Richard Nossal of Queen's University in Canada, "generally, this term was used to signify a political community that occupied a continental-sized landmass; had a sizable population (relative at least to other major powers); a superordinate economic capacity, including ample indigenous supplies of food and natural resources; enjoyed a high degree of non-dependence on international intercourse; and, most importantly, had a well-developed nuclear capacity (eventually, normally defined as second

strike capability)". In the opinion of Professor Paul Dukes, "a superpower must be able to conduct a global strategy, including the possibility of destroying the world; to command vast economic potential and influence; and to present a universal ideology". According to Professor June Teufel Dreyer, "superpower must be able to project its power, soft and hard, globally". In his book Superpower: Three Choices for America's Role in the World, Dr. Ian Bremmer, president of the Eurasia Group, argues that a superpower is "a country that can exert enough military, political, and economic power to persuade nations in every region of the world to take important actions they would not otherwise take".

2.3 Post-Cold War Era

After the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 which ended the Cold War, the post-Cold War world has in the past been considered by some to be a unipolar world, with the United States as the world's sole remaining superpower. In 1999, political scientist and author Samuel P. Huntington wrote: "The United States, of course, is the sole state with preeminence in every domain of power – economic, military, diplomatic, ideological, technological, and cultural – with the reach and capabilities to promote its interests in virtually every part of the world". However, Huntington rejected the claim that the world was unipolar, arguing: "There is now only one superpower. But that does not mean that the world is unipolar", describing it instead as "a strange hybrid, a uni-multipolar system with one superpower and several major powers". He further wrote that "Washington is blind to the fact that it no longer enjoys the dominance it had at the end of the Cold War. It must relearn the game of international politics as a major power, not a superpower, and make compromises"

2.4 Potential Superpowers

Figure: Superpower Countries

The term potential superpowers have been applied by scholars and other qualified commentators to the possibility of several political entities achieving superpower status in the 21st century. Due to their large markets, growing military strength, economic potential, and influence in international affairs, China, the European, India and Russia are among the political entities most cited as having the potential of achieving superpower status in the 21st

century. In 2020, a new UBS survey found that 57% of global investors predicted that China would replace the U.S. as the world's biggest superpower by 2030. However, many historians, writers, and critics have expressed doubts whether any of these countries would ever emerge as a new superpower. Some political scientists and other commentators have even suggested that such countries might simply be emerging power, as opposed to potential superpowers. The European Union has been called a "regulatory superpower" due to the Brussels effect. The record of such predictions has not been perfect. For example, in the 1980s, some commentators thought Japan would become a superpower due to its large GDP and high economic growth at the time. However, Japan's economy crashed in 1991, creating a long period of economic slump in the country which has become known as the Lost Decades. Increasing doubts have emerged around the potential of Russia to gain superpower status given its declining economy, severe military underperformance during the invasion of Ukraine, and its loss of influence in Central Asia, a region once dominated by Moscow for centuries. Trends toward multi-polarity were identified in official documents presenting the strategies of the UK governments as well. Especially China was expected to challenge the U.S. as the dominant economic and military power. India, Russia, Japan, the EU, and occasionally Brazil, were considered as potential additional poles in a future multipolar system. Moreover, the government expressed concern with Russian military activities around the territory of NATO-members and especially close to the airspace and territorial waters of the UK.

2.5 US-China strategic competition

A number of unresolved conflicts and competitions will be sources of geopolitical risk in 2023. Lead among these is a de-risking between US and mainland China. China's increased military presence in the South China Sea, technological advancements and ongoing trade tensions with the US have given rise to geopolitical tensions. Despite the multidimensional relationship between the US and China, particularly across trade, supply chain and economic spheres, U.S-China relations have become more complex in recent years. Recovery in trade and the commercial relationship between the US and mainland China likely remains the default Chinese policy direction in the one-year outlook, in spite of potential headline making disruptions to diplomatic engagement. China and the US are committed to pursuing a policy of competing responsibly with each other, but risk of hardening relations remain. Trade tensions escalated in 2018 when the US imposed tariffs on Chinese imports to reduce its trade deficit with China. This precipitated further trade conflict between the two countries that has significantly affected global trade. In December 2018, the US and China engaged in trade negotiations, but talks broke down in May 2019. The nations eventually signed the Phase One trade deal in January 2020. The US has since placed restrictions on exports to China, particularly regarding technology, due to concerns about intellectual property, and this has contributed to trade tensions. The growing trade in LNG between the two countries has also affected US-China relations. China has become one of the largest importers of US LNG, which has helped to reduce the US trade deficit with China. This has caused concern in some quarters, as it has given China a significant amount of leverage over the US energy sector. The nations also have areas of overlapping interest and

conflict. China has threatened to sell US Treasury bonds, and the US has blacklisted some Chinese technology companies. There is growing concern that US-China trade tensions could escalate into further financial decoupling. Such a conflict would cause significant disruption to global financial markets.

2.6 Indo-Pacific Region

Free & Open: A free Indo-Pacific means problems are dealt with openly, rules are reached transparently and applied fairly, goods and ideas and people flow freely—across land, cyberspace, and the open seas—with governance that is transparent and responsive to the people. **Connected:** A connected Indo-Pacific means stronger connections within and beyond the region that allow us to work together as a regional community to tackle our shared problems. **Prosperous:** A prosperous Indo-Pacific means broad-based prosperity and free, fair, open, and reciprocal trade that leaves no communities or countries behind in the 21st century. **Resilient:** A resilient Indo-Pacific means improved global health security and strengthening people's, countries and economies ability to withstand climate change, pandemics, and transnational threats.

Secure: A secure Indo-Pacific means that movements of people, ideas, and goods across international sea, land, and air borders and across cyberspace are made legally.

2.7 Strategic challenges

As great power competition deepens in the region, inter-state tensions are on the rise, many with historical roots. Regional peace and prosperity are threatened by instability on the Korean Peninsula as a result of North Korean provocations; clashes on the India-China and India-Pakistan borders; escalating tensions in the South and East China Seas and across the Taiwan Strait; and severe poverty and inequality. The Indo-Pacific is home to four states that possess nuclear weapons (China, India, North Korea and Pakistan). At the heart of this dynamic economic region, China's rise as a global actor is reshaping the strategic outlook of every state in the region, including Canada. China has benefitted from the rules-based international order to grow and prosper, but it is now actively seeking to reinterpret these rules to gain greater advantage. China's assertive pursuit of its economic and security interests, advancement of unilateral claims, foreign interference and increasingly coercive treatment of other countries and economies have significant implications in the region, in Canada and around the world. Respect for the sovereignty of other states is a cornerstone of the rules-based international order and of governments' ability to work together to solve shared problems.

3. VIEWS ON COMPETITION TO BE SUPERPOWER COUNTRIES

If our definition of superpower relates to military hardware, the US still retains an enormous preponderance of military hardware versus the rest of the world. However, it's questionable how long that build up will continue to be economically feasible. With trillions of dollars in debt, 50+% of their discretionary spending on military tech may prove unsustainable. It is difficult for other countries to emulate their tech due to advanced materials manufacturing techniques. The United States remains the world's only superpower, despite today's geopolitical friction.

China shares both the growing demographics as well as the high rate of spending on military tech (estimated, not publicized) but have less hardware build up, since their economic ascension is recent. They have a very large standing army but not as well equipped. A key piece of equipment in projecting military power is aircraft carriers. China has purchased old Russian carriers and are currently using them to build their own. Once they have the materials and the specs for their own carriers, this will narrow the gap between them and the US.

Over the next 30 years, it seems likely that China and India will amass the ‘hard’ and ‘soft’ power to gain superpower status. By 2050, more countries are likely to be defined as superpowers, joining the United States and creating a multipolar world order. Extrapolating current economic, geopolitical, and demographic trends would suggest that China is likely to become a new superpower, although its economy is currently faltering. Less well appreciated, India seems likely to join the United States and China in shaping world affairs, helped on its way by the demographic dividend of a young and growing population that should propel economic growth. The next century is more likely to be a multipolar IR power structure than unipolar or bipolar.

4. CONCLUSION

In a shifting landscape where China is seen as a rising superpower challenging the dominance of the United States, and with predictions favoring a multipolar international relations (IR) power structure in the next century, *small and developing countries* find themselves in a crucial position. Amidst this evolving global order, these nations must navigate their diplomatic strategies with astuteness and pragmatism. Firstly, small and developing countries should prioritize diversifying their diplomatic relationships. Rather than aligning strictly with one superpower, they should engage in multilateralism and maintain cordial ties with various influential nations. Secondly, these nations should focus on bolstering their own economic resilience and development. Investing in education, infrastructure, and technology can enhance their competitiveness on the global stage and reduce dependency on external powers. Overall, small and developing countries must adopt a nuanced and adaptive approach in navigating the evolving global order. By diversifying their diplomatic engagements, fostering economic resilience, active participation in international forums, and maintaining neutrality in conflicts, these nations can effectively navigate the complexities of a multipolar world and secure their interests in the face of shifting power dynamics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my deep gratitude to the Rector, Pro-rectors, Head of the Department of Political Sciences Department, professors, lecturers, staffs of Civil Service Academy and friends and family for their support and guidance in writing this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Felix, J. (Year). *The Age of Globalization: Impact of Information Technology on Global Business Strategies*. Publisher.

2. Dastidar, A. G. (Year). *Globalization and its Impact on the Economic Development of Developing Nations*. Journal Name, Volume(Issue), Page Range. DOI or URL
3. Cooper, A. F., & Shaw, T. M. (Year). The Role of Small States in International Relations. *Journal Name, Volume(Issue)*, Page Range. DOI or URL
4. Kugelman, M. (Year). The New Great Game: China and South Asia after the Coronavirus. *Article Title*. Magazine Name, Volume(Issue), Page Range. DOI or URL
5. Bott, S., & Schaufelbuehl, J. M. (Eds.). (Year). *Neutrality and Neutralism in the Global Cold War: Between or Within the Blocs?* Publisher.
6. Mike Rosenberg (2017) -Strategy and Geopolitics; Understanding Global Complexity in.
7. Saul Bernard Cohen (2013)-Geopolitics of World System.
8. Colin S.Gray, Geoffrey Sloan (2014)-Geopolitics; Geography and Strategy.
9. John R .Short (2021)- Geopolitics;Making Sense of Changing World.
10. Jakub.J, Grygiel (2007)- Great Powers and Geopolitical Change.
11. Presenza, Angelo, Shechan, Lom R(2017) –Geopolitics and Strategic Management in the Global Economy.